

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This thesis discusses the methodology of developing creative thinking of preschool education students.

Key words: Education, training, thinking, student, creative, methodology, gifted person, activity, flexibility of thinking, communication, modeling.

Helping students to perform independent, creative activities means creating conditions for them to determine their positions and implement them in practice, providing tasks aimed at pedagogical support of their creative activities. Strengthening national independence and making a firm decision in Uzbekistan coincides with extremely complex historical and socio-political situations. It is an even more complicated social problem to remove and cleanse citizens' minds, worldviews, and psyches from old-fashioned views, lack of initiative, stupidity, and addiction. At this level, in order to carry out large-scale and large-scale events in all aspects of society's life gradually, evenly, harmoniously and consistently, by educating young people who can meet the requirements of the new era, have a new consciousness and worldview, and who think freely, creatively and independently. cultivation is one of our most important tasks.

It is known that since the years of our country's independence, a lot of scientific and practical works have been organized and put into practice in order to improve the quality and efficiency of education. it is important to prepare them as experts at the level of being able to engage in independent practical activities. The basis of the reforms carried out by our President Shavkat Miromonovich in the field of education is the importance of achieving high efficiency in preschool education. and it is necessary to develop creativity in them, to be able to achieve a certain result through his independent thinking, creativity, and creative thinking while working with students.

The content of our article is the recommendations of our research work on the development of independent thinking, creativity, and creative thinking of preschool education students. This problem has been widely studied in the fields of higher school psychology, psychology of creativity, psychology of thinking, and the issue of formation and development of creative thinking in students has also been studied in the field of methodology of scientific creativity. Any person

acquires a certain activity experience as a result of the development of professional knowledge. That's why a person should create, enrich and complete the experience of professional activity with his creativity. A student acquires such experiences in higher pedagogical educational institutions and enriches them throughout his life. A student should always be able to demonstrate important creative skills. Only then will he be able to show his creativity during his professional activity. Today, the person-oriented approach in teaching is one of the leading tools in the formation of creativity qualities in students: "self-management", "self-development", "personal activity", "self- The use of such concepts as "self-organization" in the practice of person-oriented education can also be the main evidence. The summarizing aspect of all this is that the subject himself becomes the initiator and organizer of his learning, education and development process, that is, the learner - the student does not become the subject of knowledge, but first of all is counted as such. Thought is a high form of human mental activity; the process of reflection of objective reality in the mind.

Thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social phenomena, reality, and also the main condition for human activity. It is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and accurately than intuition, perception, and imagination. It is said to think, to reflect the things and events in reality by thinking, summarizing and mediating the connections between them. Reality is reflected in thinking, perception and imagination relatively deeper and more.

The ability to think creatively in students is an expression of the abilities and skills, will, diligence and determination of a scientist, researcher, creator, and the ultimate goal is the desire to acquire new useful scientific knowledge. The object of our research is the types of thinking and creative activities of students of higher educational institutions.

The purpose of psychological study of students' readiness for creative activity or their creative approach to their future professions is the students' environment, the characteristics of their education, their ideas about scientific and artistic creativity, professional creativity and creative activity, the student community, The goal is to create favorable psychological conditions for the creative activity of a specialist-student. As a result of the step-by-step study of the dynamics of students' readiness for creative activity - the process of growth, specific aspects of students' creative thinking are revealed. Preparing students for a creative approach to their profession is a complex process that depends on the student's needs, values, emotions and intellect, as well as professional and life motivation. By forming creative thinking in students:

- the quality and efficiency of higher education and production integration will increase;

- we will increase the number of intellectuals, creators, competitive modern personnel in the society and thereby increase the prestige of our society on the world scale;

- competitiveness of personnel, level, labor and production efficiency, level of socio-economic stability in the society will increase.

This, in turn, will certainly serve the future socio-economic and political development of our society. The analysis of different approaches shows that in order to fully study the orientation of the future teacher's professional activity to creativity, it is necessary to approach it from the point of view of the theory of attitude. Because the attitude embodies the inclinations of the person. In this way, there is an opportunity to determine the professional orientation of a person. Analyzing the factors of future teachers' choice of teaching profession, we paid attention to the extent to which students understand the importance of professional activity. Based on this, we were able to determine the following:

- the presence of interest in the educational subject;

- the presence of a desire to learn a certain subject;

- the superiority of striving to devote oneself to students and education;

- awareness of his pedagogical ability;

- strong desire to get higher education;

- the existence of a perception of the importance of the teaching profession for society;

- the presence of a tendency to pedagogical creativity;

- such as the strength of the need for financial support. The results of pedagogical support of students' creative activities are manifested in the deepening of their individuality and creative qualities. Creative thinking, in turn, enables learners to:

➤ learn independently and consciously;

➤ always moving forward;

➤ rational resolution of various conflicting and problematic situations;

➤ teaches unconventional and new ways of thinking.

Creative activity is a form of thinking, which is developed by training ability, talent, desire, innovation, creativity are signs of creative activity. The main conclusion is that if the imagination of students about creative thinking expands, the motivation of their creative activity is understood, and special

corrective methods for professional training are used, then the level of readiness for creative-creative thinking will increase consistently.

Also, the effectiveness of students' scientific and creative research, support of talented students, science olympiads, student scientific conferences, scientific and artistic circles also causes interest and motivation in creativity and the formation of relevant skills.

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